

USE OF PRODUCT LIFE CYCLE MODEL AND MARKETING-MIX DECISION-MAKING FOR ENHANCING MARKET PERFORMANCE IN BREWERY COMPANIES IN SOUTH-EAST, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT: The study examined the Use of Product Life Cycle Model and Marketing-Mix Decision-making for enhancing market performance in Brewery companies in the South-East, Nigeria. The purpose of this study was to assess the use product life cycle model for decision-making and enhancement of market performance of Brewery companies in the South-East, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The research population consists of Decision-Makers in the selected companies in the South-East, Nigeria. Thus, the population was one hundred and eleven (111). The study employed the convenience and purposive sampling techniques to select respondents for the study. Moreover, the study used the descriptive analysis such as percentage, frequency, mean, standard deviation, while factor and regression analysis were used for hypothesis testing with the aid of statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 24.0. The statistical analysis used for this work was factor and regression analysis. The results indicate that a strong and statistically significant association between Use of PLCM for decision-making and enhancement of sales volume, profit and market share of

Brewing firms in South-East, Nigeria. Based on the findings, the following conclusions were made; PLCM is used by brewery companies in the south-east, Nigeria. Furthermore, the product life cycle model enables these companies to have competitive edge over rivals. Lastly, the three hypotheses stated for the study, indicated that, there is a positive and significant relationships between sales volume, profit, and market shares of Brewery Companies in South-East, Nigeria.

Keywords: *Product Life Cycle, Marketing-Mix, Decision-making and Market Performance.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of Brewery companies in Nigeria, and the subsequent extinction of some of these Brewery Companies have called for urgent attention in Nigeria. The existence of brewery companies commenced with the establishment of Nigerian Brewery PLC in 1946. The Nigerian Brewery (NIG) PLC utilized the consumer market research was to assess market demand and to develop a market strategy for **Star Lager** that utilized advertising to show a link between drinking and modernity (Harp and Simon:2003). In 1960, star beer attained market leadership of the production of beer in Nigeria. As the sales volume and profit began to rise, it attracted new player in the market. This led to the new emergent of Brewery companies like; Guinness Plc, Consolidated (NIG.) Ltd, Golden Guinea. Intafact Beverages, International Breweries Plc, Seven-Up Bottling Ltd, Coca-Cola Nigeria Ltd, Malt Derivatives Ltd, Nigeria Distillers Limited, e.t.c. Despite the Geometric increase in these Breweries companies, studies have shown that these companies have gone into extinction. Companies like; Premier brewery Onitsha, Consolidated Brewery Awo-Omamma which was later bought over by Nigerian Brewery (Plc), Gold spot, presently acquired by Coco-Cola bottling company (Nig) Ltd. It is important to know that, the saturation of these Brewery companies has brought about stiff competition among to know that, the saturation of these Breweries companies has brought about stiff competition among these companies in Nigeria. Kotler (1997) asserted that organizations facing stiff competition should endeavour to employ strategies which output of decision-making that would enable them to surmount other competitors. Organizations such as Breweries companies, in the bid to survive in this

fierce competitive market environment tend to employ decision-making tools such as; the PLCM, as input for effective and efficient decision-making. This will enable organizations to achieve goals like; sales, profit, satisfaction, market shares, e.t.c.

According to Arlene (2007), the product lifecycle is associated with marketing management decision within businesses, and the entire product, as they go through all four primary stages; introduction stage, growth, maturity, and decline stage. Priya (2019), opined that, organizations can benefit from the PLCM in the following way(s), defining the strategies, making crucial marketing decisions, forecasting sales, having competitive edge over rivals, target market positioning, and this will help organizations such as the brewery companies to have an edge over rivals.

It is worth-noting that, grasping the concepts of the product life cycle can make the brewery companies and marketing managers to plan for innovation or modification of marketing-mix strategies (i.e. product, price, promotion and place) to address the various strategies in the product life cycle model (PLCM),as well as helping an organization to achieve its goals.

Kotler and Keller (2007) posited that, an organization's positioning and differentiated strategy must change as the product moves form one stage to another. Thus, marketing decisions regarding; product, price, promotion, and place will change as the product moves from one stage to the other in the product life cycle.

Ederewhevbe , Iweka,Ogbulie, and Egele (2021) argued that, in the first phase of the product life cycle, the marketing decision taken include; Product Decision (i.e. Product quality, Product Performance, Marketing Research for customers and Standardization or Adaptation). In the same vein, the price decision taken include; Skimming Pricing Strategy, Cost-Plus, and Penetrating Pricing Strategy. Furthermore, Ederewhevbe et al (2021) opined that, in the lunch stage, the Promotion decisions include; creation of awareness and arousing the customer's attention. While the place decisions taken include; Selective or Exclusive distribution strategy. In the second stage of the product life cycle model the Marketing-Mix Decision taken comprised of product decision (i.e. improvement of product quality, and physical product performance). However, the price decision in the growth stage are;

maintaining penetrating pricing strategy or increasing the price slightly and skimming pricing strategy. Other decisions taken include promotion decision (i.e. increase sales effort and advertising of brand image). However, the place decisions taken in the development phase are intensive decision and extensive distribution strategy. However, the price decisions taken in the third phase comprised of, price discount, price variation, cost-plus and premium-pricing strategies. It was also affirmed that, the promotion decision taken in the aforementioned stage are; persuasive advertisement and aggressive promotional strategies, e.t.c. On the other hand, the place decision taken in the maturity stage include; intensive and extensive distribution strategy.

Furthermore, Cross (2012), affirmed that, the last stage of the life cycle model is saddled with a lot of decisions. These decisions include; product decision (i.e. re-designing the product). Other decisions are price decision- these include; setting low price, and price discount. Furthermore, promotion decisions taken in the above-mentioned stage are reduction of promotional expenditure and reminder strategy. However, in place decisions, the following decisions are taken; reduction of distribution outlets and selective distribution strategy. Avrari and Krishnaswamy (2006) asserted that, the PLCM provide an important perspective for formulation of strategies, because every phase of the product is believed to have distinct characteristics that offset the operation of an organization and consequently on the marketing decision and market performance of the organization.

Uzoka (2006) affirmed that, decision is the act of choosing a plan of action from among identified and often time's analyzed possible course of action. Marketing managers take action-based decisions whenever they engage in any marketing function(s). Umar (2016), argued that, marketing decisions are in the areas of; Products, Price, Promotion and Place, with the view of increasing the market share, profit, customers satisfaction , sales volume, retaining customers and ensuring that they gain customers patronage. These decisions are important content of marketing mix, in which different aspects of these 4Ps are critically examined and selections of options are made to enable organizations achieve its goals. Thus, these decisions when rightly taken can enhance the market performance of an organization. It is

worth – noting that, as the product passes through the different stages of the PLC, marketing decisions taken relating to product are-quality, performance, brand name, safety warranty, Packaging, e.t.c. while that of Price are-Pricing strategies comprising Penetrating, Skimming, cost – plus, e.t.c. For place, it include-market coverage – selective, exclusive and intensive, and for promotion are Promotional strategies-pull and push – sales promotion, direct marketing, personal selling, e.t.c). These need to be taken by the organisation to enhance market performance.

Homburg, Grodanvic, Klarmann (2007) claimed that market performance is operational excellence of an organization's marketing activities with regards to market related goals; such as revenue, growth, market share, e.t.c. In the same vein, Suherly, Faisal, Helmi and Alexandre (2016) opined that market performance is the contribution of the marketing function for the achievement of organizational goals. These goals include; Profits, Sales, Market shares, Customers Satisfaction, Retention, e.t.c. According to Sheth, Sisodia and Sharman (2000), the goal of achieving efficiency and effectiveness is to get loyal customers at minimal experience, thereby boosting and consequently increase market performance. Thus, marketing efficiency is necessary because consumers derive the greatest possible satisfaction at the least possible cost. It is of no doubt that brewing firms in Nigeria are faced with fierce competition. Researchers have shown that the brewery companies in Nigeria started in about 1946, with the Nigerian Breweries Limited (NBL), and as at today, the industry have spread all over the country. In the South-East, Nigeria, the brewery industries are increasing at a very high rate. Beside Nigeria Breweries (Nig) Plc, a lot of brewing industries have sprung up. These industries include; Nigeria Breweries Plc, Premier Breweries, Golden Guinea, Intafact (Nig) Plc, Guinness (Nig) Plc, Consolidated Breweries, e.t.c. These industries are competing among each other, to gain control over the market, to attract attention of the customers in other to boost sales, increase market shares and profit, and to have competitive edge over rivalry firms. Amidst this competition, some of these brewery industries have gone into extinction (e.g. Premier Brewery, Onitsha, Consolidated Brewery, Awo-Omamma, -which was acquired by NBL PLC as a result of closure. This has resulted to Breweries industries looking for different marketing decision making tools- like the PLCM, to know if it can enhance its market

performance. However, it is still unclear if the use Product Life Cycle model (PLC) can be a veritable tool that can be used to develop marketing strategies that would enhance Market outcomes of brewing companies in the South East, Nigeria. The incessant rise in the establishment of Brewery companies in Nigeria today will cause a serious threat to Brewery market, in Nigeria. Researchers have shown that, the use of product life cycle model can enhance the market performance Breweries in Nigeria. Smile and Daniel (2014) informed that, the marketing-mix strategies adopted by organization in each stage of the product life cycle have a lot of impact on the sales volume, profit, e.t.c. on small and medium scale enterprises. However, it is yet to be ascertained if the use Product Life Cycle model (PLCM) can be a veritable tool that can be used to develop marketing strategies that would enhance market performance of brewery companies in the South East, Nigeria, this is the gap that this study intend to bridge.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

In a competitive market such as Nigeria, businesses are striving to gain competitive edge over rivals. In Nigeria, the Breweries Company with its brands of beer beverages is competing with each other to capture the market. This is why Sujana and Metani (2020) argued that, global economy growth is increasingly leaving to competition, especially for similar companies such as brewery companies. The number of competitors in the Brewery companies, each struggling to provide products that satisfy its target market. Thus, every Brewery companies tend to employ decision-making tools within its disposal to increase the sales volume and achieve profit on the long-run. In the bid to increase marker performance, organizations tend to employ various marketing-mix decision making tools like; the Lifecycle marketing model to formulate strategies that would enable them to increase sales, profit, customer's satisfaction, e.t.c. Scholars in the academic field have argued that , decision-making tool, like product life cycle model(PLCM) allows marketing managers to plan for forecasting and strategic planning to manage their products and services through the various phase of the PLC,(Fredrick :2003). Furthermore, Smile and Daniel (2014) informed that, the marketing strategies adopted by organizations at every stage of the PLC has a lot of impact on market performance like; sales volume,

profit, and customer's satisfaction in small and medium scale enterprise in Ghana, South Africa e.t.c. Although, researches have shown the efficacy of the use of product life cycle model and its marketing-mix strategies in the enhancement of market performance (sales volume, profit, market shares) in organizations in South-Africa, Ghana, Europe, and America Continents (Fredrick:2001; Bintu: 2017; Clark:1999 and Assad and Ramadan et al:2008). However , it is still uncertain if the Use of PLCM and the development of Marketing-Mix Strategies can enhance market performance in Breweries companies in South-East- Nigeria, this is the puzzle that this research intend to bridge. Beside, could product life cycle model (PLCM) and Its Marketing-Mix decision-making enhances sales, profit, and market share in Brewery Companies in South East States - Nigeria? The aim of this study was to assess the use of the PLC for marketing decisions making for Enhancing Market Performance of Brewery companies in the South- East Nigeria. However, specific objectives are;

1. To examine the extent to which use of product life cycle model for Marketing-Mix decision-making enhances sales volume in Brewery Companies in South-East, Nigeria.
2. To investigate the extent to which use of product life cycle model for Marketing-Mix decision- making enhances profits of Brewery Companies South-East, Nigeria.
3. To evaluate the extent to which use of product life cycle model for Marketing-Mix decision- making enhances market shares of Brewery Companies South-East, Nigeria.

While the following hypotheses were stated for the study are articulated as follows:

Hypotheses

H₀₁: The use of product life cycle model for Marketing-Mix decision-making is not significantly related in the enhancement of Sale volume of Brewery Companies in South East, Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between use of PLCM for Marketing-Mix decision-making and enhancement of Profit of Brewery Companies, in South- East, Nigeria.

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between use of product life cycle for Marketing-Mix decision-making and enhancement of Market shares of Brewing Companies in South-East, Nigeria.

11. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1.0 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Product Life Cycle Model

The Product Life Cycle is the model that seeks to describe and explain the sales of a product from its introduction stage through to its decline stage. It is a strategy tool that helps organizations to plan for new product development and refine an existing product. According to Vlad (2024), the PLC is a roadmap for marketers, helping them understand how a product evolves overtime in the market. He opined that, the evolutions of PLC phases are: development, introduction, growth, maturity and decline. It is worth-noting that the PLCM helps managers in planning and strategizing to avoid the pitfalls of the different stages. Priya (2019) argued that, the company or organization can benefit from the PLC from the following ways; easy sales forecasting, competitive advantage, defining strategies, making crucial decisions and marketing target and position and this helps an organization to have a competitive edge over its competitors. Each of these stages has its cost, opportunities and risks, and individual product differs in how long they remain at any of the life cycle stages.

2.1.2. Stages of the Product Life Cycle

1. **Introduction Stage:** This stage begins with the introduction of the product into the market. This phase is marked by minimal sales growth, and a low market share. This is because, being a newly launched product, consumers may not be aware or they may not know much about the product, (Jagran: 2015). It is interesting to know that this stage has the following characteristics;(i) high cost due to initial marketing, advertising, distribution, etc. (ii) low sales and slowly

increasing sales volume;(iii) little or no competition among competing firms, demand must be created through promotion and awareness campaign;(iv) customers must be prompt to try the product and there is little or no profit made due to high and low sales volume.

2. **Growth Stage:** At this stage, the public becomes more aware of the product; sales begin to grow and profit begins to accrue. Some of the characteristics of the growth phase involve the following ;(i) sales volume increases significantly, as the product increases in popularity, sales volume increases. Other features includes ;(ii) rise in profit, increase in public awareness as a result of the use of promotional tools, (iii) competition begins to increase with a few firms coming into the market. (iv) Lastly, increase in competition leads to price decrease, (Derek: 2021).
3. **Maturity Stage:** At this stage, sales will peak as the product reaches market saturation and competition grows increasingly. This phase is marked by the following; (i) features of the product is increased in order to resale the product;(ii) lowering of prices to fight off competition; (iii) intensifying distribution and promotional effort; (iv) using product differentiation strategies; and finding a new target market. Illensanmi (2011) argued that the third phase is longest stage in the PLC. He stresses that, this is the time that repeat business and purchases take the Place of new customer's buying. Thus, during the maturity stage the following features occur: cost are lowered, sales volume peaked and market saturation is reached, competitors increase, prices often decline as more competitors enter the market, industrial profit go down and brand differentiation and diversification is prioritized to sustain and increase shares.
4. **Decline Stage:** At this phase, sales begin to decline, profit diminish, competition stays intense the product approaches obsolescence. The features of the decline stages are ;(i) decline in sales volume as competition becomes severe and popularity of the product falls. Besides, (ii) there is a fall in price and profit and this becomes a very strong challenge to the organization. Thus, (iii) this will eventually lead to the withdrawal of the product from the marketplace, (Kotler: 1997). Below is the diagram of the product life cycle;

Fig 1-Carol (2024)

2.1.3 Marketing-Mix Decision:

In the words of Drucker (1993) in Uzoka (2006), It is the act of choosing between different courses of action. The choice is rarely as clear-cut as right versus wrong.... Sound decisions emerge from the clash of differing viewpoints and thoughtful evaluation of competing ideas and alternatives. Precisely, decision focuses on choosing a cause of action or strategies that organization execute. Thus, marketing decision is taken daily to achieve organizational goals. The general goals of the marketing decision are to take decision that would satisfy the target market and to develop perceived value of the product and produce a favorable response that would lead to profit making. It is worth-noting that, most marketing decisions fall into one of the four main categories (i.e. the marketing mix), which comprise of; product, price, promotion and place.

Product Decisions: product decisions pertains to aspect such as physical attributes including size, style, specification, e.t.c. and the management of product lines. Furthermore, product decisions are influenced by the extent to which organizations most modify its offering along the standardization-adaptation spectrum in response to varying market conditions, (www.fao.org).

Price Decision: Maximillian (2015) posited that, Price represents the total value a customer sacrifices to obtain the benefits of owning or using a product or service. It is a vital component of the marketing mix. Kotler and Keller (2012) said pricing decisions are clearly complex and difficult. They argued that pricing choices should align with the company's overall marketing objectives, intended customer segments, and branding positioning. The price of an organization is critical to the survival of the firm. Umar (2016) informed that marketing decision relating to price include; pricing strategy (penetrating, cost-plus, skimming etc.), seasonal pricing, cash and early payment discounts, price flexibility, volume discounts or wholesale pricing etc. Thus, an organization must take decisions with regard to the above mentioned prices to maximize its profit.

Promotion Decision: In marketing, promotion encompasses all forms of communication aimed at informing or convincing the target audience about the value of a product, service, brand, or idea. Its primary objective is to build awareness, stimulate interest, drive sales, or enhance brand recognition and loyalty, (McCarthy; 1964). Promotion decisions include, decisions on promotional strategy (push, pull, etc.), advertising, personal selling, sales promotions, public relations and publicity, etc. These strategies are very essential in the process of the promotional activities.

Place Decision: Place (distribution) is a vital ingredient of the total marketing mix, that ensures the product availability to the right target markets, at the right quantity, at the In proper condition, at an appropriate price, and at the optimal time at the right time, anytime and all the time, (Prezi;2020). Some examples of place /distribution decisions are; market coverage (Exclusive, Intensive and Exclusive), distribution channels, inventory management, transportation, warehousing, etc.

2.1.4. Market Performance

Homburg, Grozdanovic, Warmann , (2007) are of the view that, market performance is the effectiveness and efficiency of organization's marketing activities with regards to market related goals, such as revenue, Sales, growth, profit, market shares, e.t.c. In the same vein Clark(1999), in his history of market performance measures showed how traditional financial measures (profit, sales, cash flow) expanded to a range of

non financial (market shares, quality, customer satisfaction, loyalty, brand equity), input (marketing audit , efficiency/effectiveness, multivariate analysis). Ambler and Kokkinaki (1997), informed that, among the recurrent measures of market performance are sales, market shares, profit, purchase intention, e.t.c. Thus, these measures (i.e. sales, profit, market shares, e.t.c.) can be used as indicators of market performance in an organization.

Sales: These refer to operations associated with the sale of products or the volume of items sold over a specific timeframe.. The delivery of goods or services for cost is also considered a sale, (Wikipedia, 2017). Furthermore, Sales represent revenue a company generate from selling goods or services to its customers, (investopedia; 2021). According to Aashish (2022), the term sales include all activities involved in selling an offering in exchange for something in value. Sales are often seen as the essential fuel that keeps a business alive in the long term. However, while the term sales refer to the actual transaction, the term sales also encompass all activities which lead to this transaction. In the same vein, Sales can be understood as a mutual agreement where one party delivers a good or service in return for monetary compensation and passes the title to it, in exchange for a certain price in current money. Sales department often plays a significant role in the success of a business. It is the only department that is responsible to bring or generate money to the organization. As a business owner or practitioner, if you are not concerned with maximizing sales, your organization may not be as profitable as you hope it would be. It is important to know that, without sales of product or service, a business becomes a hobby or a charitable organization, (Kimberlee; 2019) .it is worth-noting that, sales play key role in the building of loyalty and trust between customer and business. Trust and loyalty are the main reason why a customer would choose to recommend and organization to a friend, or family member or write a great review of an organization's product service ([www.oxford college of maketing.com](http://www.oxfordcollegeofmarketing.com)). Shreyasi (2021) also informed that, as the blood circulation of a human body keeps a man alive and in sound health, so do the sales strengthen the organization. The more is the sales, the more is the profit. He also stressed that, increasing sales means growth for the firm. Moreover, if the sales fall, it is fatal, because sales are the life blood of the business. Thus, for an organization to grow, it must ensure that many sales are made,

to continue to grow and survive in a competitive market such as the brewery industries.

Profit: According to Kenton (2021), profit is described as the financial gains realized when revenue generated from business activity exceeds the expenses, cost, and taxes in sustaining the activity in question. Furthermore, Horton (2020) argued that, profit is an absolute number determined by the amount of income or revenue and beyond the costs or expenses a company incurs. He stressed that no matter the size of an organization or in the industry in which it operate; a company's objective is to make profit. Thus an organization, such as the brewery industry will use all available marketing –mix strategies to achieve its profit. In the same vein, profit can be seen as a financial gains especially the difference been the amount earned and amount spent in buying, operating, or Producing Something. (www.businessdictionary.com). It can also be seen as surplus remaining after total cost are deducted from total revenue and the basis on which tax is. It is essential to know that profitability is the main objective of every business organization. Thus, without profit it will be practically difficult for a business to survive for a long time, (simoom; 1999). It is significant to measure present and past profit, and estimating future profit. This is because; it will make a firm to guide its revenue and expenses to ensure that the stated objective(s) of the firm is achieved. Profitability refers to a company's capacity to efficiently use its resources to produce income that exceeds its costs. In other words, it reflects the firm's ability to earn profits from its operations. The other three are efficiency, insolvency, and market prospects. Investors, creditors and managers use these key concepts to evaluate how well a company is doing and the future it could have if operations are properly managed. Conclusively, every organization or business expert, expect to earn a profit, because profits are the engine room for success. The growth and survival of any business depends on the profit earned by such organization. Thus, profit should not just be viewed as the reward to owners of business rather it should be related with the interest of other segments of the society. Profit is the medium for deciding not just the economic, but level of management efficiency and achievement of societal objective(s), (Ifediba, Ederewhevbe and Ogbulie; 2022).

Market Share: This refers to the section of a market controlled by a particular company's product. Market share is simply the percentage of a certain sector that your product, service or beverage is responsible for, calculated by sales (airfocus.com/glossary). Furthermore, Anderson (2021) posited Market share refers to a company's portion of total industry sales. The firm with the highest share is considered the market leader. Furthermore, Cross (2018), argued that, market share is said to be a key indicator of market competitiveness that is, how well a firm is doing against its competitors. The metric, Supplemented by changes in sales revenue, helps manager evaluate both primary and selective demand in their market. This is, it enables them to judge not only total market growth or decline but also trends in customers' selections among competitors. It interesting to know that, market share is a key indicator of a company's competitiveness. When a company increases its market share, this can improve its profitability. (www.investopedia.com).

Leslie (2022) opined that, a company's market share is an important area for businesses because; it's an indicator of a company's profitability and success. It can give a signal of dominance in an Industry and how well a company's revenue-generating effort are working to achieve its business goal. It is essential to know that, there different ways by which a company can increase its market shares.

Sales Volume: According to Google .com (2021) Sales volume refers to the number of units your company sells during a specific reporting period. This period could be a month, a quarter, or a year depending on what level of sales volume you're seeking to analyze. Investors frequently look at sales volume to assess the health of a growing or contracting company. These are activities related to selling or the number of goods sold in a given period.

2.2.0 Empirical Review

Geoffrey, Harrison, Oforegbuna and Donatus, (2025) the examined the Marketing Mix Optimization in Nigeria's Brewing Industry: A Regression and Geometric Programming Approach (Case Study of Nigerian Breweries PLC) The study investigated the impact of marketing mix elements—Product, Price, Promotion, and Place (4Ps)—on the revenue and profit of Nigerian Breweries Plc (NBL) from 2013

to 2022, using secondary data. Regression analysis was employed to assess the relationship between the 4Ps and revenue, while geo-metric programming optimized the marketing mix for profit maximization. The results indicated that Product and Promotion positively influence revenue, whereas Price has a negative effect. Geometric programming revealed the optimal contributions to profit: Product (99.80%), Price (0.09%), Promotion (0.06%), and Place (0.05%). These findings highlight the importance of balancing revenue-driven and profit-oriented strategies, emphasizing that distribution capacity plays a key role in maximizing the effectiveness of other marketing mix elements. Distribution limitations can hinder the impact of production, promotion, and pricing. Although, there some agreement with the findings of this work in terms of product, promotion and distribution in enhancing sales / revenue, and profit , there are slight deviation in price. This shows that, at each stage of PLC model decision taken can enhance the sale volume profit and market share in Brewery firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Illesanmi (2011) carried out a study on the significant of distribution channel and PLC in the management of an organisation, the Nigerian experience. The aims of the study were to assess the significance of distribution channel and Product Life Cycle on the survival and growth of business organizations in Nigeria. The Study was a conceptual framework of distribution and PLC. The findings of the study indicated that, the distribution channel and product life cycle are highly significant in the management of an organisation irrespective of its size. In addition the work established that, the value of the Product Life Cycle stemmed from the facts that, it enables manager to know why typically happens in the distribution of product at different phases of the PLC. Moreover, the result showed that channel decision is not static once- and for all choice, but it is a dynamic part of the overall marketing planning. Thus, he concluded that channels and the PLC offer value insight into allocating resources, analyzing further problems, and opportunities and make managers thinks strategically. Illesanmi (2011) argued that, when a proper channel choice and physical distribution strategy is designed, the growth of the product is not only enhanced, but a relative market share growth of the company is guaranteed.

Gbolagade, Adesola and Oyewale (2013) carried out a research work on an evaluation of the role of marketing strategy in enhancing business performance among selected SMEs in Oloyole Local Government Area Ibadan, Nigeria. The aim of the study was to examine the impact of marketing strategies on business performance. The survey research design method was used in the study which involves using a self – design questionnaire in collecting data from hundred and three (103) respondents. The instrument used in the study was close – ended questionnaire. The Correlation coefficient and multiple regression analysis were used to analyze the data with the aid of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 20. The results showed that the independent variables (i.e. product, promotion, price, packaging and after sales services) were significant joint predictors of business performance in terms of profitability, market shares, return on investment and expansion. The study therefore recommended that, small medium enterprises (SMES) operators should produce quality products, charge competitive prices, position appropriately, use attractive package for the product, engage in after sales services and provide other distinctive functional benefits to consumers.

Sharma (2013) conducted a research on the marketing on different stages of the product life cycle and its marketing implications of FMCG (fast moving consumers goods) products. The objective of the study is to identify how far the concepts of product life cycle can help the organization to gain higher market shares and sustain competitive advantage in (FMCG) fast moving consumer goods. The study used the desk research technique to offer a theoretical background to the study. The findings of the research that, the use of the PLC model has a significant impact on the success of the business strategy and the associated corporate performance. Furthermore, the study showed that, there are different strategies that are offered in the different stages of the product life cycle. Moreover, the study indicated that, the PLC model can be use to optimize a product's revenue in respect of its positioning in a market during the first stage of the PLC. Conclusively, the study affirmed that, the product life cycle model can be use to determine sales volume, market share, profitability and survival of firms.

Bintu (2017) carried out a research work on the effect of marketing mix strategy on performance of small scale business in Maiduguri metropolitan, Borno State, Nigeria. The aim of the study was to explore how marketing mix elements are managed and their impact on the performance of small scales enterprises in Maiduguri. The population of the study comprises of all small scale enterprises within Maiduguri metropolitan. The stratified sampling technique was used to group respondents into three main trade areas of refilling, personal services and repairs and production. Multiple regressions were used to analyze the data collected for the study. The work revealed that marketing strategy (product, price, promotion and place) were significantly independent on joint predictors of business performance. Each possesses its own distinct contribution and impact on profitability, market share, customer satisfaction and market expansion of small business. However, the relationship between business performance and promotion was negative but significant. This showed that promotion is very relevant in communication that brings about and creates awareness, interest and trials and this will in turn lead to increase in sales, profit and market shares.

Mohammad, Saghalian and Alizadeh (2017), conducted a study on prioritization of expanded marketing-mix in different phases of the PLC; the case of food industry. The main primary objective of the study was to prioritize the marketing-mix in each phase of the PLC using the Analytic Network Process (ANP) approach. For this reason, a questionnaire was designed, and a survey of food industry marketing managers in Mashhad was conducted. The result showed that, between 7ps of marketing-mix, in the first stage of the PLC, “promotion”, while in other stages, price takes precedence. Moreover, in the different phases of the PLC, each marketing- mix has some sub-indices, the result showed that, among all sub-indices, “advertising” in the introductory, “high price” in the Growth stage, moderate price in the maturity stage, and in the decline stage, “rebate” possess the highest weights. The work also established that, prioritization of the marketing-mix can be used at different stages of the product life to help managers for better allocation of their resources and increase in profitability. The researchers concluded that, application of a suitable marketing mix across various stages of the product life cycle is one of the challenges confronting, managers in all industries. They asserted that, lack of the

PLC and the appropriate marketing strategies in each stage, lead to the selection of suitable strategies and destroy the competitive advantages of a firm. Thus, it is important for managers to have appropriate marketing strategies in several phases of the PLC, in other to help marketing managers allocate their scarce resources between competitive marketing activities in different stages of the product life cycle for achieving the highest productivity. From the above study, a proper prioritization of the marketing strategies in the various stages of the PLC can lead to the enhancement of sales volume profitability, e.t.c of an organization.

Asaad, Ramadan, Hekar, Daleen, Cihad and Shamd (2018), carried out a study to examine the impact of marketing strategy in the different phases of the PLC on organization performance as a private business with special reference to the Cihan University Duhok camps KRS – Iraq. The research aimed to examine how marketing strategies enabled business owners to maintain growth over time. The survey research design method was employed in the study, which involves using a self – design questionnaire in collecting data from hundred (100) respondents. The instrument in the study was a closed – ended questionnaire. The multiple regression analysis was used to evaluate the data with the aid of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 22. The results Showed that the independent variables (i.e. marketing strategy (MS), Service Strategy (SS), pricing strategy (PS) promotional strategy (PRS), place strategy (PLS), After sales service strategy (ASSS), Higher education marketing strategies (HEMS), and social media marketing strategies (SMMS) were significant joint predictors of business performance in terms of profitability, market share, return on investment, and expansion. However, the study discovered that promotion has the strongest profit significant effect on performance. The study recommend that since operators should produce quality more services, change competitive prices, position appropriately, use attractive services for the university, engage in after sales services and provide other distinctive functional benefits to students.

Cross (2018) carried out a study to examine the effect of marketing strategy on organization performance. The aim of the study was to assess the effect of marketing strategy on organizational performance of Nigeria bottling company in Kaduna state.

A sample size of 245 was obtained from the population of 636 @ 5% error tolerance and 95% of freedom, using Yamane's statistical formula $245(100\%)$. The questionnaire was designed in likert scale format. The researcher conducted a pre-test on the questionnaire to ensure the validity of instrument. Furthermore, the Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was used to test the hypotheses. The findings revealed that, there is no relationship between product strategy and the level of profit, there is no relationship between promotional strategy and sales volume, no substantial correlation exists between price strategy and the market share and lastly, there is no meaningful association between place and the level of customer loyalty in Nigeria Bottling Company, Kaduna. However, the study revealed that, the utilization of product strategy enhances the level of profit in Nigeria Bottling Company, Kaduna. He stressed that; product is about the quality, design, features, brand name, and sizes and these influences the level of profit of Nigeria Bottling Company. Moreover, the study revealed that, the use of promotional strategies enhances sales volume in Nigeria Bottling Company. And also provides target audiences all the accurate information they need to take decision

Abebe (2019) conducted an investigation into the impact of marketing strategy on performance of SMES evidence from selected manufacturing enterprises in southern region, Ethiopia. The study was aimed to investigate the effect of marketing strategy on business performance of selected small and medium manufacturing enterprises in southern, Ethiopia. The researcher employed casual research design. However, to collect primary data, self-administered questionnaire were distributed to 250 owners /managers of SMES by using purposive sampling, followed by stratified random sampling technique. The Pearson correlation and multiple regressions were used to analyze the data. The result showed that, a substantial correlation exists between product, price, promotion, and place of small and medium manufacturing enterprises (SMMES), whereas the relationship between place and SMES performance was found significantly negative. Thus, to achieve the objectives of an organization, SMES should endeavour to produce innovative (new design feature, varieties) products, charge affordable prices and disseminate tailored promotion. Although, this work was emphatic on the strategies the strategies that can enhance performance of small medium enterprises business in selected manufacturing firms in Ethiopia, it

was not critical on the stages in the PLC that these marketing decisions will be taken. This of course created a gap that this work tends to bridge.

Muhammad (2019) conducted a research to investigate the association between four elements of marketing –mix concept: product, price, place and promotions, with organizational performance. The research conducts a comprehensive review of prior studies on the concept of the marketing mix. The descriptive analysis was employed to evaluate the best practices among 7ps of the marketing mix strategy towards organization performance. The result showed that, a positive correlation exists between marketing mix and customer satisfaction. Furthermore, the findings indicated that, the effective marketing-mix decision strategy of product, price, place, and promotion will help organization to increase profit for the business not only in the short –term but also in the long-term. Thus, a critical review of the PLC can influence the choice of a good use or application of the marketing- mix strategy to enhance the sales volume of an organization. This is what necessitated this work.

Adefulu and Adeniran(2019), conducted a research on channel strategy and marketing performance of selected consumer goods firms in Lagos state. The target market consists of five hundred and ninety-two (592) employees in the sales and marketing department of selected firms. The purposive and stratified sampling techniques were adopted for the study. Moreover, to analyze the data, descriptive statistics, simple linear and multiple regression correlation, with aid of SPSS 23.0 version were employed. The result showed that, channel strategies adopted by the firms are predictors of marketing performance (sales volume) of selected consumers' goods firms in Lagos state Nigeria. Moreover, the results indicated that, direct channel strategy showed no meaningful association with sales volume growth higher market share, consumer loyalty, dealer retention and loyalty. However, the indirect channel strategy, through the retailers had significant relationship with market share, consumer loyalty and dealers retention. Thus, this finding suggests that, if a proper channel of distribution strategy is employed, the market performance (i.e. sales volume, market shares, profit, and dealer retention) will be enhanced.

Ihemereze (2020) conducted an investigation into the impact of marketing mix strategy on sales performance of Brewing firms; a study of Nigerian Breweries

Enugu, Nigeria. The objective of study was to examine influence of marketing mix strategy on sales performance on brewing firms. The research design for the study was descriptive survey design and questionnaire served as the instrument for data collection. The target Population of the study was one hundred and thirty – five (135) which consisted of the management staff and major distributors of Nigerian Breweries Enugu,

Enugu State. The data collected were presented and analyzed using simple percentage and chi – square Statistical tool. The study discovered that high product quality enhances sales performance of brewing firms. Beside, the penetrating pricing strategy enhances sales performance of brewing firms; nearness of distribution place to target market enhances sales performance of brewing firms. Thus, a good implementation of the 4ps will make the firms to achieve its goal. However, the above-mentioned work did not review the phases of the PLC that the marketing-mix strategies would be carried out to enhance sales volume in Nigerian Breweries Company. Thus, this research work intends to bridge this gap, hence this work was carried out.

2.3.0 Theoretical Framework

The product life cycle theory is an economic theory that was developed by Raymond Venon in 1966, in response to the failure of Heckscher-ohin model to explain the observed pattern of international trade. The theory posits that during the initial phase of a product life cycle, all components associated with the product come from area where it was invented. The product life cycle is based on the following assumptions; (i.) every product has a limited life,(ii.) product life cycle is conducted for a category, (iii) different buyer groups buy product during different phases,(iv.) the shape of the product life differs for different types of product and (v.) the PLC requires different marketing strategies. The alight from the above-mentioned assumptions implied that, no matter how good a product is, there is a life span. Some of the products are short-lived, while others stay for a long. Beside, every product category passes through a cycle and each buyer group buy product during these phases. Thus, from the introduction stage down to the decline stage, there are few medium, and light buyers, and this have a lot of implication to the marketers and the organizations. In the same

vein, the shape of the PLC differs for different types of product. Some product(s) linger in the introduction stage for a long time before they enter the growth stage, while products like; tea, coffee, and beverages have undergone long maturity period. Lastly, the changes in the market shares, sales, and profitability during these phases of the PLC poses different challenges, problem and opportunities to the organization. Thus, to overcome these challenges, organizations need to implement separate marketing-mix decision strategies in the four (4) stages of PLC and make valuable marketing-decisions to be able to satisfy the firms' objectives (profit, sales, market shares, e.t.c.) and its target market.

This theory is relevant to this study because, there is no one way of making decisions. The decision taking by a firm, depends on what it intend to achieve. Thus, every organization will make its decision on the product, price, promotion, and place in the various phases of the PLC based on what is needed by its target market. Understanding the environment in which the organization operates and having the right Marketing-mix in leadership team is very important for the success and growth, and this would contribute to the overall performance of the firm, such as increase in profit, market share, sales, e.t.c. A critical analysis of the PLC shows a typical organization, such as the brewery firms operating in an environment where the right decision when taken will enable the firm to achieve its goals of increase in profit, market shares, sales, e.t.c. The research framework adopted in the study with respect to the PLC and marketing decision making is enhancing market performance is portrayed in fig.1 below.

Fig.2 Product life cycle, marketing mix and market performance

Source: Ederewhevbe, I.G & Iweka, A. N (2025)

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The choice of the research design stemmed from the fact that, survey research design afforded the researcher quantitative data, that can be analyzed using quantitative analytical tool. Besides, it allows the researcher the opportunity to collect information by asking questions from the respondents.

The targeted population of the study consisted of those involved in decision making in the Brewery Companies in the South-East, Nigeria. However, because of the sensitivity in decision making, the population under study consisted of the line functional managers and some other staff that are involved in marketing-decision making as it concerned product development and marketing. The population of the brewery firms in the South-East are; Golden Guinea (Nig.) Plc.-18, Guinness (Nig.) Plc.-32, Nigerian Breweries (Nig.) Plc.-41, and Intafact Beverages (Nig.) Ltd-20. Hence, the total population; is a total of 111. While the convenience and purposive sampling techniques were used to select respondents for the study. The primary source of data collection was basically through questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed in 5 point likert scale-Very High-5, High-4, Moderate-3, Low-2 and Very Low-1. All analysis were completed with the aid of computer programming (i.e. statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 24.0. The statistical analyses used for this study are: Descriptive statistic, Factor analysis and Regression analysis.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis one

There is no significant relationship between the use of product Life Cycle Model for Marketing-Mix decision and sales volume of brewing firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Table 1

Hypotheses Testing Goodness of Fit	Model	R ²	P-Value
Ho 1a: There is no Significant 0.004 Significant	Sales= -1.489		0.995

Relationship between use the
 Product of Life Cycle Model for + 1.342 Introduction
 Marketing-Mix Decision-Making Stage
 and enhancing of Sales volume of
 Brewery Companies.

Ho 1b: There is no Sales = -0.437 0.978 0.011
 Significant

Significant Relationship + 1.095 growths Stage
 between the use product of
 Life Cycle Model for marketing-Mix
 Decision-making and enhancing
 Sales volume of Brewery Companies.

Ho: 1c: There is no significant Sales = - 0.430 0.984
 0.016 Significant

Relationship between the use + 0.906 maturity
 Product of Life Cycle Model, for Stage
 Marketing-Mix Decision and enhancing
 Sales volume of Brewery Companies.

Ho: 1d: There is no significance Sales = - 0.286 0.996
 0.002 Significant

Relationship between the use of + 1.933 decline stage.
 Product Life Cycle Model for .
 Marketing-Mix Decision making
 and enhancing Sales
 Volume of Brewery Companies.

Source; Output SSPSS, 2025

The table 1 showed the various P-value of hypotheses one (1) Indicated that, the P-value of (HO1a) 0.004 is less than less than 0.05 ($0.004 < 0.05$). In the same vein, the P-value of (HO1b) 0.011 is less than 0.05 ($0.011 < 0.05$). Furthermore, the P-value of (HO1C) 0.016 is less than 0.05 ($0.016 < 0.05$). Lastly, the P-value of (Ho1d) 0.002 is less than 0.05. ($0.002 < 0.05$). This showed that the alternate hypothesis which states that, there is a significant relationship between the use of product life cycle model Marketing-Mix Decision Making and enhancement of sales volume is accepted. The table 1 showed clearly the Goodness of fit. It depicts that there is a significant relationship between Product Life Cycle Model and Sales volume of Brewery Companies in the South-East, Nigeria. Furthermore, the correlation (R^2) of the hypothesis (i.e. Ho 1a, Ho1b, Ho 1c, and Ho1d) is very strong and positive ($R^2 - 0.995$, $R^2 - 0.978$ and $R^2 -0.984$, $R^2-0.996$), indicated that, there is a strong and positive relationship between the independent variable (I.e. the stages in the Product Life Cycle Model) and the dependent variable (sales volume). This implied that, changes in the introduction stage of the product life cycle with respect to marketing-mix decision taken (i.e. in terms of increase Product quality, low price, creation of product awareness and selective channel of distribution), Growth (Modifying product quality, increase in price, product persuasion and intensive distribution strategy), Maturity (Product modification, competitive pricing strategy, aggressive promotional strategy and intensive distribution strategy) and Decline (maintaining product Quality, reduction of Price, decrease in promotion tools and selective distribution Strategy) it will invariably have a positive and significant impact on the sales volume on Brewery Companies in the South-East, Nigeria. This findings conforms to the study of Geoffrey, Harrison, Oforegbuna and Donatus, . (2025) that examined the Marketing Mix Optimization in Nigeria's Brewing Industry: A Regression and Geometric Programming Approach (Case Study of Nigerian Breweries PLC) The study investigated the impact of marketing mix elements—Product, Price, Promotion, and Place (4Ps)—on the revenue and profit of Nigerian Breweries Plc (NBL) from 2013 to 2022, using secondary data. Regression analysis was employed to assess the relationship between the 4Ps and revenue, while geo-metric programming optimized the marketing mix for profit maximization. The results indicated that Product and Promotion positively influence revenue, whereas Price has

a negative effect. Geometric programming revealed the optimal contributions to profit: Product (99.80%), Price (0.09%), Promotion (0.06%), and Place (0.05%). These findings highlight the importance of balancing revenue-driven and profit-oriented strategies, emphasizing that distribution capacity plays a key role in maximizing the effectiveness of other marketing mix elements. Distribution limitations can hinder the impact of production, promotion, and pricing. Although, there some agreement with the findings of this work in terms of product, promotion and distribution in enhancing sales / revenue, and profit, there are slight deviation in price. This shows that, at each stage of PLC model decision taken can enhance the sale volume profit and market share in Brewery firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Bintu (2017) carried out a research work on the effect of marketing mix strategy on performance of small scale business in Maiduguri metropolitan, Borno State, Nigeria. The aim of the study was to explore how marketing mix elements are managed and their impact on the performance of small scales enterprises in Maiduguri. The population of the study compromises of all small scale enterprises within Maiduguri metropolitan. The stratified sampling technique was used to group respondents into three main trade areas of refilling, personal services and repairs and production. Multiple regressions were used to analyze the data collected for the study. The work revealed that marketing strategy (product, price, promotion and place) were significantly independent on joint predictors of business performance. Each possesses its own distinct contribution and impact on profitability, market share, customer satisfaction and market expansion of small business. However, the relationship between business performance and promotion was negative but significant. This showed that promotion is very relevant in communication that brings about and creates awareness, interest and trials and this will in turn lead to increase in sales, profit and market shares. Besides, the above study showed, decision taken in each of the stages of the PLC can have effect of the profit, market share and sales volume on a company. This is in conformity with the finding of this study, which established that, there is significant relationship between the use of product Life Cycle Model for Marketing-Mix decision and sales volume of brewing firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two 2

There is no significant relationship between the use of product life cycle model for Marketing-Mix Decision-Making and Enhancement of Profit of Breweries Companies in the south-east, Nigeria.

Table 2 The Summary of the Profit Models

Hypothesis Testing	Model	R ²	P- value
Goodness of fit			
Ho2a: There is no significant Significant	Profit = -1.662	0.928	0.037
Relationship between the use Of Product Life Cycle Model For Marketing-Mix Decision-Making And Enhancement of profit of Brewery Companies.	+ 0.617 Introduction stage		
Ho2b: There is no significant 0.025 Significant	Profit =- 0.049	0.950	
Relationship between the use Of Product Life Cycle Model For Marketing-Mix Decision-Making And Enhancement of Profit of Brewery Companies.	+ 1.015 Growth Stage		
Ho2c: There is no significant Not good	Profit = -2.328	0.823	0.093
Relationship between the use Of Product Life Cycle Model For Marketing-Mix Decision-Making And enhancement of profit of	+ 0.454 Maturity Stage		

above analysis of hypothesis Two confirmed that, there is a strong and positive link between the use of the Product Life Cycle Model for Marketing-Mix decision-making and enhancement of profit of Brewery firms in the South-East, of Nigeria. The findings showed that any change in the PLC model will have a corresponding change in the marketing-mix decision of brewery companies, and this can lead to changes in the profit of the brewery companies. Mohammadi, Saghaian, and Alizadeh (2017), carried out a study on Prioritization of Expanded Marketing Mix in Different Stages of the Product Life Cycle: The Case of Food Industry. They employed the marketing concepts and methods while prioritizing the marketing mix approach for products can play an important role in increasing sales and ensuring greater success in the marketplace. The main objective of this study is to prioritize the marketing mix in each stage of the product life cycle using the ANP approach. For this purpose, a questionnaire was designed, and a survey of food industry marketing managers in Mashhad was conducted in 2015. The results show that between 7P's of marketing mix, in the introductory stage of the product life cycle, "promotion," and in other stages "price" have the highest priority. According to the fact that each marketing mix has some sub-indices, the results show that among all sub-indices, "advertising" in the introductory stage, "high price" in the growth stage, "kind of payment" in the maturity stage, and in the decline stage, "rebate" possess the highest weights. Therefore, prioritization of the marketing mix can be used at different stages of the product life cycle to help managers for better allocation of their resources and increase profitability. The aforementioned study is in agreement with the findings of this work that, asserted that, the PLCM can be used to make decision that can enhance the profit of brewery companies in south-east, Nigeria.

HYPOTHESIS THREE (3)

There is no significant relationship between the use of Product Life Cycle Model for Marketing-Mix Decision-Making and enhancement of Market Share of Brewery firms in the South-East, Nigeria.

Table 3 The Summary of the Market Share Model is shown below

Hypothesis Testing value	Model Goodness fit	R ²	P-
Ho3a: There is no significant 0.028	Market share = 0.114 Significant	0.944	
Relationship between the use Of PLC Model For Marketing-Mix decision-making And enhancement of market share of Brewery Companies.			
Ho3b: There is no significant 0.028	Market share = 0.430 significant	0.968	0.016
Relationship between the use Of Product life cycle Model For Marketing-Mix Decision-making And Enhancement of Market Share of Brewery Companies.			
Ho3c: There is no significant 0.002	Market share = - 0.286 significant	0.996	
Relationship between the use Of Product Life Cycle Model For Marketing-Mix decision-making And enhancement of market Share of Brewery Companies.			
Ho3d: There is no significant 0.169	Market share = 2.302 Not-good	0.691	
Relationship between the use Of Product Life Cycle Model For Marketing-Mix decision-making And Enhancement of Market Share of Brewery Companies.			

Sources: Output SPSS, 2025

In Ho3d the model market shares = 2.302 + 1.561 decline stage is not good. Since the P-value of 0.135 is greater than 0.05 (0.135 > 0.05). This implies that, at decline stage of the product life cycle and market share, the model is not good for prediction.

Table 3 showed that, the various P-value of hypothesis Three (3). It indicated that, the P-value of H_03a 0.028 is less than 0.05 ($0.028 < 0.05$). Furthermore, the P-value of H_03b 0.016 is less than to 0.05 ($0.016 < 0.05$). This showed that, the model for market share in the first and second phases of the PLC, are good for prediction. Conversely, the P-value of H_03c 0.996 is greater than 0.05 ($0.996 > 0.05$), this showed that, the Model for market share for maturity stage of the product life cycle is good for prediction. However, and the P-Value of H_03d 0.169 is greater than 0.05 ($0.169 > 0.05$). A critical look on the aforementioned analysis showed that the model for market share in the decline stages in the PLC Model is not good for prediction.

Furthermore, table 3 showed that, the correlation (R^2) of hypothesis three (3) H_03a , H_03b , H_03c , H_03d and their corresponding value of 0.944, 0.968, 0.996 and 0.691 indicated that, there is a positive and strong relationship between the independent variable (i.e. the stages in the product life cycle model) and the dependent variable (Market Share). This implied that, at the introduction stage of the product life cycle, the decision taken (i.e. product quality, low price, creation of awareness, and selective channel of distribution), Growth stage (modifying the quality of the product, increase in price, product persuasion, and intensive distribution strategy), maturity stage (concentrate/modify the features of the product, competitive pricing strategy, aggressive promotion strategy) and decline stage (maintaining product quality, reduction of price, decrease in promotional tools and selective distribution strategy) have a positive impact on the market share of Brewery firms in South-East, Nigeria. Conclusively, the above analysis of hypothesis Three established that, there is a positive and significant relationship between the use of the Product Life Cycle Model for Marketing-Mix Decision-making and Enhancement of Market Share of Brewery firms in the South-East, of Nigeria. The findings showed that any change in the Product life cycle model (i.e. the first, second, third and last stages) will have a corresponding change in the marketing-mix decision of Brewery Companies, and this can lead to changes in the Market Share of the brewery companies in South-East, Nigeria. The above mentioned study gives credence to the work of Sharma (2013), that conducted a research on the marketing on different stages of the product life cycle and its marketing implications of FMCG (fast moving consumers goods)

products. The objective of the study was to identify how far the concepts of product life cycle can help the organization to gain higher market shares and sustain competitive advantage in (FMCG) fast moving consumer goods. The study used the desk research technique to offer a theoretical background to the study. The findings of the research indicated that, the use of the PLC model has a significant impact on the success of the business strategy and the associated corporate performance. Furthermore, the finding indicated that, there are different strategies that are offered in the different stages of the product life cycle model, it can be use to optimize a product's revenue, market share and profits in the different phases of the PLC. Thus, the PLC model as a decision making tools, can be use to enhance the market share, sales and profit of brewery firms in south east Nigeria.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

After a careful analysis of data collected from the respondents, the following findings were established; it was discovered that, all the brewery companies studied in the South-East, Nigeria make use of the PLC model for marketing decision-making.

The study also indicated that, the brewery companies studied asserted that, the use of PLC model enable them to have competitive edge over rivals.

Moreover, the study confirmed that, all the Brewery Companies in the South- East, Nigeria have multiple line range of products.

Furthermore, the study showed that, majority of the brewery company's products goes through the introduction, growth, maturity, and decline stages. However, the findings of this work indicated that, bulk of the brewery companies products were between Growth and Maturity stage of the product life cycle.

The result from the first hypothesis indicated that, there is a positive relationship and significant between the use PLC Model for marketing decision-making and the enhancement of sale volume of brewery companies in South-East, Nigeria. The model formulated for sales indicated that it is good for prediction.

In the same vein, the result from the second hypothesis indicated that, there is a positive and significant relationship between the use of PLC for marketing decision-making and profit of Brewery Companies in the South-East, Nigeria. However, In Ho2c and Ho2d the models for Profit are not good, since the P-value of 0.093 and 0.148 are greater than 0.05, ($0.093 > 0.05$), ($0.148 > 0.05$), the information showed that, the PLC Model and Profit (in the Maturity and Decline stage), the models are not good for prediction. Finally, the findings from the third hypothesis confirmed that, there is a positive relationship between the use of PLC model for marketing decision-making and market share of Brewery firms in the south-east, Nigeria. However, In Ho3d the model market shares = $2.302 + 1.561$ decline stage is not good. Since the P-value of 0.135 is greater than 0.05 ($0.135 > 0.05$). This implies that, at last phase of the PLC and market share, the model is not good for prediction.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the work, the following conclusions were made:

The study established that, the brewery companies in the south-east, Nigeria, make use of the PLC model for marketing decision-making. Furthermore, the study confirmed that, the use of product life cycle model, enable the Brewery companies in the South-East, Nigeria to have competitive edge over rivals. Moreover, it was also established that, all the Brewery companies studied in the south-east

Nigeria, have multiple line range of products. Furthermore, it was confirmed it this work that, the product of the brewery companies studied goes through the different stages of the PLC. However, it was confirmed that, a larger percentage of the Brewery companies products were in the growth and maturity stage. It was also confirmed that, in the first hypothesis, there is a positive and significant relationship between the use of PLC model for marketing decision-making and enhancement of sales volume in Brewery companies in South-East, Nigeria. Moreover, the model formulated for hypothesis one indicated that, the model is good for prediction.

In addition, it was affirmed that, in the second hypothesis- there is a positive and significant relationship between the use of product life cycle model for marketing decision-making and enhancement of profit in Brewery companies in South-East,

Nigeria. However, In Ho2c and Ho2d the models for Profit are not good, since the P-value of 0.093 and 0.148 are greater than 0.05, ($0.093 > 0.05$), ($0.148 > 0.05$), the information showed that, the product life cycle and Profit (in the Maturity and Decline stage), the models are not good for prediction.

Finally, we concluded that, in the third hypothesis, there is a positive and significant relationship between the use of product life cycle for marketing decision-making and enhancement of market shares in Brewery companies in the South-East, Nigeria. However, In Ho3d the model market shares = $2.302 + 1.561$ decline stage is not good. Since the P-value of 0.135 is greater than 0.05 ($0.135 > 0.05$). This implies that, at decline stage of the product life cycle and market share, the model is not good for prediction.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made;

- 1) Brewery firms in Nigeria should endeavour to make use of the product life cycle model to enable them make viable decision that would make achieve their goals.
- 2) Brewery firms in Nigeria should endeavor to analyze the marketing –mix decision in each of the phases of the PLC to enable take appropriate marketing decision that would enhance market performance.
- 3) The product life cycle model should be extended to other industries to enable them know the various marketing-mix decision strategies that would be taken at different stage of the product life cycle that would enhance market performance in terms of profit ,sales, market share, and customers satisfaction, e.t.c.
- 4) The research work also recommended that, the PLC model should be extended to other Geopolitical zones of Nigeria, with the view of knowing its validity for making viable marketing decision in enhancing market performance.

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